

EXAMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRINCIPALS' ORGANIZATIONAL LONELINESS AND JOB SATISFACTION LEVELS

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Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the relationship between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction of principals according to various parameters. Descriptive research model is used in the study and universe is consisted from principals who participated in "Acquiring Formation Course Management II", organized by Malatya Provincial Directorate of National Education. 233 volunteer principals, who answered the data collection tool properly and completely constituted the sample. "Loneliness at Work Scale" developed by Dođan et al. (2009) is used as the data collection tool. Descriptive statistical calculations on the dataset are conducted and the lowest and the highest scores, standard deviation scores and arithmetic means are calculated. Besides these, t-test and one-way variance analysis (ANOVA) are performed through the data obtained. If ANOVA test results with significant differences, the multiple comparison tests are preferred to determine from which group or groups the difference is originated. Scheffe test is used for the multiple comparisons of average scores in case of equal distribution of the group variances. The results of the study reveal that there is a significant and small positive correlation between Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction perceptions of principals. Emotional deprivation and social friendship dimensions correlated at medium-level and positively with organizational loneliness. Social friendship dimension and job satisfaction also correlated positively at medium-level. A significant relationship between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction in the positive direction is another important result of this research.

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Keywords: organizational loneliness, job satisfaction, principal, school administrator

1. Introduction

The modern world has caused many new perceptions and experiences in today's people. People in the New World order have been introduced to the concept of "loneliness in society" (popularly called "being alone in crowds") and perhaps this centuries-old depression has become more of a painful side, with technological developments and commercial activities becoming more prominent. This situation, which makes people unhappy and reduces the energy of life, is seen in business life as it is in every area.

Managerialism is perhaps one of the most professional and professional aspects of this loneliness. Because managerialism is perhaps one of the main positions in which this loneliness is mostly and easily felt, as because the subordinate relationship that determines organizational function naturally brings with it the psychology of loneliness. In this sense, being an administrator in an institution is a tiring process, full of difficulties despite all the respect it also brings. The manager is also the person who can contribute to the organization at the same time, being able to be the leader and able to carry it to the future in the direction of its goals. How the manager feels in his organization is of great importance in this respect.

2. Literature Review

Loneliness is a subject that can be associated with a concept that has many organizational and administrative contexts (Yılmaz & Aslan, 2013; Ođuz & Kalkan, 2014; Demirbař & Hařit, 2016) and one of these concepts is job satisfaction. Research reveals that there is a close link between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction (Chan, & Qiu, 2011; Schumaker et al., 1993; Yılmaz, 2008). There is a mediating role of sense of loneliness between ethical leadership and perceived organizational climate (Erođluer & Yılmaz, 2015) and perceived organizational support seems to have no effect on the loneliness of academics in business life (Çetin & Alacalar Çakır, 2016). There is a significant relationship between social environment and loneliness (Erdil & Ertosun, 2011); and organizational longevity negatively affects the organizational commitment (Ayazlar & Güznel, 2014).

Job satisfaction, on its own and associated with other topics, has received considerable attention and processing in the last period. Considering the continuity and development of the organisation, it can be assumed that the emphasis on work in this

area is not based on unfair causes. Findings (Demirtaş, 2010; Izgar, 2008; Madenođlu et al., 2014; Yazıcıođlu, 2010) support the idea that employees will be happier if they feel job satisfaction in their organizations; and most probably, such a situation will contribute to job performance and organizational commitment.

Moving from all these points, it is important to determine the relationship between the perception of loneliness and job satisfaction in business life and how and in what direction this relationship is going. The research of these two concepts in terms of management and in particular principal is of great importance in terms of educational institutions that guide the future of society and their schools.

The concept of loneliness carries a multi-dimensional content closely related to organizational individual and social life. Galanki (2004) describes loneliness as a universal human experience with emotional, cognitive, motivational, and behavioural dimensions. Organizational loneliness, which is one of these dimensions, is important both for the workers and the organizational implications they realize. It seems that two types of organizational loneliness have been emphasized in the literature. These are described as social and emotional loneliness, and while social loneliness is expressed as "*the absence of social relations among individuals or the absence of an individual in an accepting community*" (Russell et al., 1984; Őiřman & Turan, 2004: 119-120); emotional loneliness is expressed as "*the absence of a sincere and close ties to others and often a feeling of anxiety and emptiness*" (Russell et al., 1984; Wright, Burt & Strongman, 2006).

Besides the results of many the researches, it can be predicted that organizational loneliness have an important effect on the perception of job satisfaction and organizational life. Job satisfaction is the degree to which the need and desire of the workers are met. Evans (1997) defines the concept of job satisfaction as the mood that arises as a result of meeting one's needs related to job. In addition to physical and mental health, the emotions that individuals have about their institutions and jobs, financial returns, the pleasure of working together are the determinants of job satisfaction (Bařaran, 2000). In other words, organizational life has an important effect on the perception of job satisfaction as well as individual expectations. Failure to reach saturation will disappoint the employee. Such a result can either contribute to motivate the worker to become more motivated or cause the person to chaos and have mental problems in some cases and ignore his/her expectations.

When the concept of job satisfaction is approached from the managerial perspective, it is concluded that employees who are motivated towards the goals of the organization will contribute not only to the organisation but also to the success of the administrator. In this context, principals need shareholders who are highly motivated and therefore serve intensively for the purposes of the organization. In addition to

financial motivation, behaviours such as appreciation, recognition and support should also contribute to job satisfaction (Sertçe, 2003).

There are studies that show that there is no meaningful relationship between job satisfaction and loneliness (Şişman & Turan, 2004); there are also studies that show that there is a negative relationship between loneliness and life satisfaction levels (Yılmaz & Altınok, 2009). In addition, there is a significant relationship between teachers' 'organizational silence and their perceptions (Nartgün & Demirer, 2016) and teachers' job satisfaction and managerial behavior (Yılmaz & Boğa Ceylan, 2011). There is also a research result which shows loneliness as a tool for physical and emotional exhaustion (Stephenson & Bauer, 2010).

It should not be forgotten that many factors including rewards, punishment, social relations, etc. should be taken into account as a complex set of combination besides job satisfaction in the increase of productivity (Davis, 1988). Believing in work and being proud of it is among the results of job satisfaction.

Today, business life means meeting most of the social needs of individuals as well as the need to maintain their lives. Naturally, these needs require the employees in the organizational setting to be intensive communication, relationships and interaction. Sharing many things brings them closer to each other and keeps them from being lonely. Therefore, employees, who spend most of their time in their organizations, tend to reach all emotional and spiritual satisfactions there besides the financial ones. Thus, on the one hand, these interactions and exchanges among the employees increase their job satisfaction; on the other hand, perceptions of organizational loneliness can be reduced through the pattern of these cooperative relationships. This "organizational loneliness-job satisfaction" relationship is a particularly important issue and should be dealt with in terms of school organizations whose input-output is human and works in a human-focused approach and their principals.

This study aims to investigate the relation between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction of principals according to various parameters.

Here are the investigation questions:

1. What are the perceptions of principals about organizational loneliness and job satisfaction?
2. Is there a significant difference in principals' perceptions of organizational loneliness and job satisfaction according to;
 - a. Gender,
 - b. Major Field of Graduation,
 - c. Education level,
 - d. Faculty,

- e. Stage of schools they work,
 - f. their professional year of experience,
 - g. Number of students in the school,
 - h. Number of teachers in the school?
3. Is there a relationship between principals' perceptions of organizational loneliness and job satisfaction?
 4. Do the principals' perceptions of organizational loneliness affect their job satisfaction level?

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Research Model

This study intended to investigate the relationship between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction of principals according to various parameters by using relational research model (Balçı, 2007; Hsu, 2005; Yıldırım & ŐimŐek, 2005).

3.2. Population and Sample

School principals who participated to "Acquiring Formation Course Management II", organized by Malatya Provincial Directorate of National Education and held between 14-18.09.2015 constitutes the population and Sample Universe of this study. Scale was applied to all of the principals attended to the course during the research period. As a result, sample of the study is constituted from 233 volunteer school principals, who answered the data collection tool properly and completely.

3.3 Data Collection Tools

A. Loneliness at Work Scale (LAWS): In this study, as the data collection tool "Loneliness at Work Scale (LAWS)" developed by Wright, Burt & Strongman (2006) and adapted to Turkish by Dođan et al. (2009) was used. In order to investigate the psychometric properties of Turkish version of the LAWS, 254 females, 182 males and totally 436 employees participated in the study. Employees with an age range between 18 and 52 were included in the sample of the study. The psychometric properties of scale were investigated by test re-test, Cronbach's alpha, exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis and criterion related validity methods. In order to determine the construct validity of LAWS, exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis was conducted. The factor analysis resulted in two factors; emotional deprivation and social companionship, which is same factor structure as the original form. The Cronbach's alpha for the LAWS was 0.91, emotional deprivation was 0.87 and social

companionship was 0.83. The computed test re-test reliability coefficient was found to be 0.82 for the LAWS, 0.78 for emotional deprivation and 0.80 for social companionship. As a result, the psychometric properties of the Turkish version of LAWS showed a satisfactory level of reliability and validity in Turkish employee and can be used for similar studies as a valid data collection tool.

B. Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale: Minnesota Job satisfaction Scale (1967) was developed by Weiss, England, David and Lofguist. This scale aims to evaluate the job satisfaction level of the employees in different sectors. There are also some adaptations and many applications of exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses of this scale as a short and long form in Turkey. In this study, short form of the scale with 20 items is used. The scale is formatted as follow: "1-Totally Disagree", "2-Disagree," "3-Moderately Agree", "4-Strongly Agree", "5-Totally agree" and high scores obtained from the whole scale show that a high level of perception of job satisfaction about their administrative duties.

3.4 Data Collection and Analysis

In the study, descriptive statistical calculations were made on the obtained data in order to reveal the effects of the levels of organizational loneliness felt by principals on their job satisfaction. The lowest and the highest scores, standard deviation scores and arithmetic means were calculated. In addition to these, t-test and one-way variance analysis (ANOVA) were performed through the data gathered. Before the both analyses, the research data was controlled for if it meets the necessary assumptions for the implementation of the test. If ANOVA test results with significant differences, the multiple comparison tests were used to determine from which group or groups the difference is derived from. In case of equal distribution of the group variances, for the multiple comparison of average scores Scheffe Test was preferred (Büyüköztürk, 2010). The correlation coefficient was calculated by Pearson Moments Multiplication analysis in order to show how the relationship between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction levels are felt by principals. Correlation coefficient is an approach used to find and interpret the amount of the relationship between two variables (Büyüköztürk, 2010, 31). In order to determine the effects of organizational loneliness perceived by principals on their job satisfaction levels, multiple linear regression analysis was performed on the data obtained. However, before the regression analysis was performed, it was checked whether the data could meet the assumptions needed to perform the test. In order to be able to apply multiple regression analysis, it is necessary to find a linear relationship between predictive (independent) variables and dependent

variables with at least interval scale and continuity of measurements of dependent variables (Büyüköztürk, 2010; Çokluk, et al., 2010).

Binary correlation coefficients between the independent variables were examined in order to determine whether there was a multiple-connection problem among the independent variables studied in the research. As a result of the analyses, it was determined that the binary correlation coefficients of the independent variables change between ".34" and ".70".

4. Results and Discussion

In the following part of the study data collected from the survey were analysed in tables.

4.1 Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction Levels of Principals

Results of the analysis, carried out to determine principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness and job satisfaction, are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Perceptions of Principals about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction

Dimension	Number of Items	Lowest Score	Highest Score	$\bar{X}$	Std. Deviation
Emotional Deprivation	9	1.11	3.22	2.25	.35
Social Friendship	7	2.43	4.71	3.76	.44
Organizational Loneliness (Total)	16	2.19	3.56	2.91	.24
Job Satisfaction	20	2.29	4.85	3.63	.57

According to the data in Table 1, organizational loneliness value was found to be 2.25 for "Emotional Deprivation" dimension, 3.76 for "Social Friendship" dimension and 2.91 for total score. This implies that school principals participating in the survey expressed their organizational loneliness levels as; "low" in "Emotional Deprivation" dimension, "high" for "Social Friendship" dimension and "medium" for total scale. From the analysis of the same table, it is understood that level of job satisfaction is "high" for principals.

4.2.1 Analysis of Principals' Perceptions of Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to Gender Variable

The findings of the t-test, performed to determine if the principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness and job satisfaction varies according to gender variable, are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of Principals' Perceptions of Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to Gender

Dimension	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	S	sd	t	p
Emotional Deprivation	Female	38	2.36	.32	231	2.21	.020*
	Male	195	2.23	.35			
Social Friendship	Female	38	3.57	.49	231	2.96	.003*
	Male	195	3.80	.42			
Organizational Loneliness	Female	38	2.89	.27	231	.54	.587
	Male	195	2.91	.23			
Job Satisfaction	Female	38	3.45	.51	231	2.11	.025*
	Male	195	3.67	.58			

T-test results given in Table 2 show that perceptions of administrators on “Emotional Deprivation” dimension indicate a significant difference in favour of female administrators [$t_{(231)} = 2.21, p < .05$] and their perceptions on “Social Friendship” dimension show a significant difference in favour of male administrators [$t_{(231)} = 2.96, p < .05$]. There has been no significant difference found when administrators' perceptions about organizational loneliness considered as a whole [$t_{(231)} = 2.21, p > .05$]. While job satisfaction parameter considered alone a significant difference [$t_{(231)} = 2.11, p < .05$] was found favouring male administrators.

4.2.2 Analysis of Principals' Perceptions about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to Major Field of Graduation Variable

One-way variance analysis (ANOVA) was performed in order to determine whether the principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness and job satisfaction vary according to their major field of graduation and result are given in Table 3.

One-way variance analysis (ANOVA) results in Table 3 show that, principals' perceptions of both organizational loneliness and its dimensions [$F_{(3, 229)} = .375, p > .05$] and job satisfaction [$F_{(3, 229)} = 1.145, p > .05$] do not reveal a significant difference according to their major fields.

Table 3: Comparison of Principals' Perceptions about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to Major Field of Graduation Variable

Dimension	Brans	N	$\bar{X}$	Std. Deviation	F	p	Difference
Emotional Deprivation	1. Natural Sciences	36	2.29	.31	.510	.675	-
	2. Social Sciences	84	2.23	.38			
	3. Primary School Teacher	83	2.23	.30			
	4. Fine Arts Teacher	30	2.30	.40			
	Total	233	2.25	.35			
Social Friendship	1. Natural Sciences	36	3.74	.37	.351	.788	-
	2. Social Sciences	84	3.80	.44			
	3. Primary School Teacher	83	3.73	.43			
	4. Fine Arts Teacher	30	3.75	.56			
	Total	233	3.76	.44			
Organizational Loneliness	1. Natural Sciences	36	2.93	.20	.375	.771	-
	2. Social Sciences	84	2.92	.26			
	3. Primary School Teacher	83	2.89	.21			
	4. Fine Arts Teacher	30	2.93	.29			
	Total	233	2.91	.24			
Job Satisfaction	1. Natural Sciences	36	3.60	.47	1.145	.332	-
	2. Social Sciences	84	3.71	.53			
	3. Primary School Teacher	83	3.55	.57			
	4. Fine Arts Teacher	30	3.68	.77			
	Total	233	3.63	.57			

4.2.3 Analysis of Principals' Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction Perceptions According to Education Level Variable

In order to determine whether perceptions of Principals about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction vary with level of education, Kruskal Wallis-h test was performed. In addition Mann-Whitney U test was applied to the dimensions which show a significant difference in order to clarify the origin of difference.

Table 4 demonstrates that considering their education levels, organizational loneliness perceptions of administrators show similarity but their job satisfaction perceptions show difference [$\chi^2_{(2)} = 9,36, p < 0,05$]. Multiple comparisons performed by applying Mann-Whitney U test indicates these differences occur between associate degree holders and post-graduates favoring associate degree holders ($\bar{X} = 3.81$); and

between under-graduate and post-graduate groups by favoring under-graduate degree holders ($\bar{X} = 3.69$).

Table 4: Comparison of Principals' Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction Perceptions According to Education Level

Dimension	Education level	N	$\bar{X}$	Mean	Std. Deviation	χ^2	sd	p	Significant Difference
Emotional Deprivation	1.Asso. Degree	13	2.28	128.00	.31	3.80	2	.149	-
	2.Under-Graduate	161	2.22	111.28	.36				
	3.Post-Graduate	59	2.31	130.18	.32				
	Total	233	2.25		.35				
Social Friendship	1.Asso. Degree	13	3.87	138.31	.34	1.40	2	.499	-
	2.Under-Graduate	161	3.75	115.57	.45				
	3.Post-Graduate	59	3.76	116.21	.42				
	Total	233	3.76		.44				
Organizational Loneliness	1.Asso. Degree	13	2.98	132.31	.22	2.97	2	.226	-
	2.Under-Graduate	161	2.89	111.98	.24				
	3.Post-Graduate	59	2.95	127.34	.25				
	Total	233	2.91		.24				
Job Satisfaction	1.Asso. Degree	13	3.81	141.50	.30	9.36	2	.009*	1-3
	2.Under-Graduate	161	3.69	123.10	.55				2-3
	3.Post-Graduate	59	3.44	94.95	.64				
	Total	233	3.63		.57				

4.2.4. Analysis of Principals' Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction Perceptions According to Faculty They Graduated Variable

Results of the applied t-test, in order to show if any difference exist at principals' organizational loneliness and job satisfaction perceptions according to the faculty they graduated, are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Comparison of Principals' Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction Perceptions
 According to Faculty They Graduated

Dimension	Faculty	N	$\bar{X}$	Std. S.	sd	t	p
Emotional Deprivation	Faculty of Education	162	2.26	.32	231	.70	.485
	Other Faculties	71	2.23	.40			
Social Friendship	Faculty of Education	162	3.77	.44	231	.66	.506
	Other Faculties	71	3.73	.45			
Organizational Loneliness	Faculty of Education	162	2.92	.22	231	1.10	.274
	Other Faculties	71	2.88	.28			
Job Satisfaction	Faculty of Education	162	3.58	.62	231	1.9	.024*
	Other Faculties	71	3.74	.43			

The t-test results indicate “Emotional Deprivation” [$t_{(231)} = .70, p > .05$], “Social Friendship” [$t_{(231)} = .66, p > .05$] and as a whole “Organizational Loneliness” [$t_{(231)} = 1.10, p > .05$] perceptions of principals did not produce a significant difference depending on faculty they graduated. Faculty of education graduates have a lower level of job satisfaction ($\bar{X} = 3.58$) compared to other faculty graduates ($\bar{X} = 3.58$) and there is a significant difference in favor of the administrators graduated from other faculties [$t_{(231)} = 1.9, p < .05$] was found.

4.2.5. Analysis of Principals' Perceptions of Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to the Stage of Schools They Work Variable

One-way variance analysis (ANOVA) was performed in order to determine whether the principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness and job satisfaction vary according to the stage of schools they work and results are shown in Table 6.

Statistical analysis in Table 6 shows that, stage of schools which administrators work does not create a significant difference for both organizational loneliness [$F_{(3, 229)} = 1.340, p > .05$] and job satisfaction [$F_{(3, 229)} = 1.430, p > .05$] perceptions.

Table 6: Comparison of Principals' Perceptions of Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to the Stage of Schools They Work

Dimension	Stage of Schools They Work	N	$\bar{X}$	Std. Deviation	F	p	Difference
Emotional Deprivation	1. Pre-School	31	2.39	.33	2.138	.096	-
	2. Primary School	83	2.22	.31			
	3. Middle School	52	2.21	.35			
	4. High School	67	2.25	.38			
	Total	233	2.25	.35			
Social Friendship	1. Pre-School	31	3.69	.46	.858	.463	-
	2. Primary School	83	3.76	.41			
	3. Middle School	52	3.72	.50			
	4. High School	67	3.82	.41			
	Total	233	3.76	.44			
Organizational Loneliness	1. Pre-School	31	2.96	.25	1.340	.263	-
	2. Primary School	83	2.89	.22			
	3. Middle School	52	2.87	.27			
	4. High School	67	2.94	.24			
	Total	233	2.91	.24			
Job Satisfaction	1. Pre-School	31	3.69	.61	1.430	.235	-
	2. Primary School	83	3.54	.57			
	3. Middle School	52	3.61	.57			
	4. High School	67	3.73	.56			
	Total	233	3.63	.57			

4.2.6. Analysis of Principals' Perception about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to Their Professional Year of Experience

One-way variance analysis (ANOVA) was performed according to year of seniority parameter to determine whether, principals' perceptions of organizational loneliness and job satisfaction vary.

According to variance analysis in Table 7, principals' perception about organizational loneliness and its dimensions [$F_{(3, 229)} = .963, p > .05$] do not show a significant difference with their professional year of experience, but their job satisfaction perception represent a difference for [$F_{(3, 229)} = 5.50, p < .05$]. Scheffe test was performed to determine which group caused the difference. Results exhibit that 0-1 years experienced administrators have more job satisfaction compared to 2-6 years experienced ones and 12 and more years experienced administrators also have a higher degree of job satisfaction compared to 2-6 years experienced ones.

Table 7: Comparison of Principals' Perception about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction According to Their Professional Year of Experience

Dimension	Year of Seniority	N	$\bar{X}$	Std. Deviation	F	p	Difference Scheffe
Emotional Deprivation	1. 0-1	64	2.27	.35	.737	.096	-
	2. 2-6	71	2.26	.38			
	3. 7-11	41	2.29	.38			
	4. 12 and more	57	2.19	.25			
	Total	233	2.25	.35			
Social Friendship	1. 0-1	64	3.72	.46	1.176	.463	-
	2. 2-6	71	3.69	.48			
	3. 7-11	41	3.84	.36			
	4. 12 and more	57	3.84	.40			
	Total	233	3.76	.44			
Organizational Loneliness	1. 0-1	64	2.90	.25	.963	.263	-
	2. 2-6	71	2.88	.28			
	3. 7-11	41	2.96	.19			
	4. 12 and more	57	2.91	.20			
	Total	233	2.91	.24			
Job Satisfaction	1. 0-1	64	3.79	.55	5.50	.001	1-2 4-2
	2. 2-6	71	3.43	.60			
	3. 7-11	41	3.57	.53			
	4. 12 and more	57	3.74	.52			
	Total	233	3.63	.57			

4.2.7. Analysis of Principals' Perceptions about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction according to Number of Students in the School Variable

One-way variance analysis was conducted in order to display the effects of number of students in the school on administrators' organizational loneliness and job satisfaction perceptions.

As a result of performed variance analysis, no significant difference was found for administrators' perceptions about organizational loneliness [$F_{(2, 230)} = .060, p > .05$] and job satisfaction [$F_{(2, 230)} = .836, p > .05$].

Table 8: Comparison of Principals' Perceptions about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction according to Number of Students in the School

Dimension	Number of Students	N	$\bar{X}$	Std. Deviation	F	p	Difference
Emotional Deprivation	1. 0-199	99	2,28	.38	2.103	.124	-
	2. 200-599	85	2.19	.28			
	3. 600 and more	49	2.30	.37			
	Total	233	2.25	.35			
Social Friendship	1. 0-199	99	3.72	.41	1.976	.141	-
	2. 200-599	85	3.84	.48			
	3. 600 and more	49	3.72	.40			
	Total	233	3.76	.44			
Organizational Loneliness	1. 0-199	99	2.91	.26	.060	.942	-
	2. 200-599	85	2.91	.25			
	3. 600 and more	49	2.92	.17			
	Total	233	2.91	.24			
Job Satisfaction	1. 0-199	99	3.62	.53	.836	.435	-
	2. 200-599	85	3.68	.66			
	3. 600 and more	49	3.55	.48			
	Total	233	3.63	.57			

4.2.8. Analysis of Principals' Perceptions about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction according to Number of Teachers in the School Variable

Table 9 denotes the outcomes of F test applied so that to display the differences in Principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness and job satisfaction according to number of teachers in the school.

Table 9: Comparison of Principals' Perceptions about Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction according to Number of Teachers in the School

Dimension	Number of Teachers	N	$\bar{X}$	Std. Deviation	F	p	Difference
Emotional Deprivation	1. 1-20	126	2.27	.36	.804	.449	-
	2. 21-40	65	2.21	.35			
	3. 41 and more	42	2.25	.29			
	Total	233	2.25	.35			
Social Friendship	1. 1-20	126	3.73	.44	.832	.436	-
	2. 21-40	65	3.82	.46			
	3. 41 and more	42	3.76	.41			
	Total	233	3.76	.44			
Organizational Loneliness	1. 1-20	126	2.91	.25	.004	.996	-

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Loneliness	2. 21-40	65	2.91	.27		
	3. 41 and more	42	2.91	.13		
	Total	233	2.91	.24		
Job Satisfaction	1. 1-20	126	3.64	.59	.047	.954
	2. 21-40	65	3.62	.62		-
	3. 41 and more	42	3.62	.42		
	Total	233	3.63	.57		

It is observed from Table 9 that principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness [$f_{(2, 230)} = .004, p > .05$] and job satisfaction [$f_{(2, 230)} = .047, p > .05$] do not show a significant difference according to the number of teachers in the school.

4.3. Relationship between Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction Perceptions of Principals'

Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients are calculated for testing if a significant correlation exist for administrators' Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction perception levels and results are given in Table 10.

Table 10: Analysis of Correlation between Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction Perceptions of Principals

Dimensions	1	2	3	3
1. Emotional Deprivation	-			
2. Social Friendship	-.223**	-		
3. Organizational Loneliness	.631**	.615**		
4. Job Satisfaction	-.112	.475**	.287**	-

**p<0.01

As it can be depicted from the correlations in Table 10, Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction perceptions of principals' have a significant, small positive correlation ($r = .287, p < .001$). If only dimensions of organizational loneliness is considered, a small negative correlation ($r = -.223, p < .001$) has been observed between emotional deprivation and social friendship dimensions. Emotional deprivation ($r = .631, p < .001$) and social friendship ($r = .615, p < .001$) dimensions correlated at medium-level and positively with organizational loneliness. Social friendship dimension and job satisfaction also correlated positively at medium-level ($r = .475, p < .001$).

4.4. Effects of Organizational Loneliness Perceptions of Principals on their Job Satisfaction Level

Multiple linear regression analysis performed to explain effects of principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness and its dimensions (independent variable) on their Job Satisfaction (dependent variable) is given in Table 11.

Table 11: Regression Analysis of Effects of Organizational Loneliness Perceptions of Principals on their Job Satisfaction Level

Variable	B	Standard error	β	t	p	İkili r	Kısmi r
Coefficient	1.338		-	3.298	.001		
Emotional Deprivation	-.011	.108	-.123	1.715	.088	-.112	-.395
Social Friendship	.626		.473	7.946	.000	.475	.464
Organizational Loneliness	-.20		-.008	.114	.910	.287	-.007
R= .475	R² = .225						
F₍₂₋₂₃₀₎ =33.431	p=0,000						

Table 11 reveals predictive level of principals' organizational loneliness perceptions on job satisfaction. It states that regression models relates "Emotional Deprivation", "Social Friendship" and as a whole organizational loneliness variables to job satisfaction perception significantly (R= .475, R²= .225; F₍₂₋₂₃₀₎ =33.431, p<0,01).

Order of importance of predictor variables according to standardized regression is as follows: Social Friendship (β =.473), Organizational Loneliness (β =-.008), and Emotional Deprivation (β =-.123). When significance test for regression coefficients are considered for predictor variables, it is found that only "Social Friendship" dimension is a significant predictor for job satisfaction.

Organizational loneliness and its dimensions, emotional deprivation and social friendship variables together explain 22.5% of variation in principals' job satisfaction perception. In other words organizational loneliness perceived by principals' affects their job satisfaction 22.5 percent.

5. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, it was aimed to investigate the relationship between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction levels, which principals perceive, on various variables, and to determine the effects of principals' perceptions of organizational loneliness on their job satisfaction levels.

According to the data, principals participating in the survey expressed their organizational loneliness levels as; "low" in "Emotional Deprivation" dimension,

“high” for “Social Friendship” dimension and “medium” for total scale. Based on this result, it can be argued that principals do not feel loneliness in their schools because of their satisfaction with work relations, friendship in school and positive relations with their colleagues. On the other hand, school principals' intense organizational loneliness in the dimension of "social friendship" can be explained by the inadequacy of social relations and interactions in their schools, as well as the limited participation of principals in these activities.

The fact that principals have job satisfaction at "high" level is another important result of the research. This result can be evaluated in the way that principals find their profession important and satisfactory in terms of social reputation and status as well as organizational rewards. The perceptions of principals about organizational loneliness and its dimensions and job satisfaction have been examined in terms of various variables. According to the scale and the dimensions of the scale, the perceptions of the principals do not show any significant difference in terms of the branch, the education level, the number of teachers and students in the school. On the other hand, the perceptions of the principals who participated in the study are significant in terms of gender, education level, faculty and their professional year of experience. It is possible to evaluate the statistical differences as follows:

Results show that perceptions of principals on “Emotional Deprivation” dimension indicate a significant difference in favour of female administrators and their perceptions on “Social Friendship” dimension show a significant difference in favour of male administrators. There has been no significant difference found when administrators’ perceptions about organizational loneliness considered as a whole. We can explain the fact that female principals are more emotionally deprived than men as they generally have a more emotional nature than men as gender and may reflect these characteristics more in their individual and organizational lives. Turkey's social dynamics and value judgments can play a role in male principals' job satisfaction being higher than their female counterparts. The male dominant society structure, together with the social status and dignity provided to the male principals, also brings them positive organizational attitudes and thus this can raise the perceptions of male principals' job satisfaction.

Organizational loneliness perceptions of principals show similarity but their job satisfaction perceptions show difference. These differences occur between associate degree holders and post-graduates favouring associate degree holders; and between under-graduate and post-graduate groups by favouring under-graduate degree holders. According to this, it seems that there is an inverse relation between the level of education of the principals and the perceptions of job satisfaction. This extraordinary

finding can be interpreted as the principals' independent evaluation of the administrative position they are in and the sense of satisfaction that this position makes them feel independent of academic competence and pedagogic competence.

The t-test results indicate that Organizational Loneliness perceptions of principals did not produce a significant difference depending on faculty they graduated. However, faculty of education graduates have a lower level of job satisfaction compared to other faculty graduates and there is a significant difference in favour of the principals graduated from other faculties. This finding can be explained by the fact that the administrators of the faculty of education have to take courses related to classroom and school management during their pre-service training and therefore the level of their readiness is high and expectations may have increased.

According to analysis, principals' perception about organizational loneliness and its dimensions doesn't show a significant difference with their professional year of experience, but their job satisfaction perception represent a difference. Results exhibit that 0-1 years experienced administrators have more job satisfaction compared to 2-6 years experienced ones and 12 and more years experienced administrators also have a higher degree of job satisfaction compared to 2-6 years experienced ones. Acting from this result, it is found that the principals having minimum and maximum seniority in management have more job satisfaction than the other groups. The job satisfaction of school principals with 0-1 year seniority can be explained by the enthusiasm of the new start to the profession and the sense of satisfaction given by having achieved this position. On the other hand, we can explain the job satisfaction of school principals who have 12 years and more seniority with the organizational and professional satisfaction given to the person having such status for years.

There is a significant and small positive correlation between Organizational Loneliness and Job Satisfaction perceptions of principals. When, dimensions of organizational loneliness are considered, a small negative correlation has been observed between emotional deprivation and social friendship dimensions. Emotional deprivation and social friendship dimensions correlated at medium-level and positively with organizational loneliness. Social friendship dimension and job satisfaction also correlated positively at medium-level. A significant relationship between organizational loneliness and job satisfaction in the positive direction is another important result of this research.

Multiple linear regression analysis performed to explain effects of principals' perceptions about organizational loneliness and its dimensions on their Job Satisfaction reveals that order of importance of predictor variables according to standardized regression is as follows: Social Friendship, Organizational Loneliness, and Emotional

Deprivation. When significance test for regression coefficients are considered for predictor variables, it is found that only "Social Friendship" dimension is a significant predictor for job satisfaction. Organizational loneliness and its dimensions, emotional deprivation and social friendship variables together explain 22.5% of variation in principals' job satisfaction perception. Although this effect is relatively small, it may indicate that principals' perceptions of organizational loneliness play a decisive role in job satisfaction. When the results of the research are evaluated in general, it can be argued that principals have a high level of job satisfaction, which is an important gain in terms of education system.

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